

Monitoring of Chromatic Dispersion in Multiband Access and Metro Converged Optical Network

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Abstract We study the performance of chromatic dispersion monitoring over S, C and L band of different fibers with a multiband bandwidth/bitrate variable transceiver. We integrate our monitoring solution in an optical networking testbed to demonstrate its accuracy with heterogeneous fiber topology. ©2024 The Author(s)

Introduction

Delivering higher capacity at the lowest possible cost has historically been the main challenge in optical communications. With Shannon capacity almost saturated, research now focuses on investigating alternative directions. At the same time, new challenges arise from the rapid growth of network segments like access and metro. Multi-domain optimization of the network as a whole [1] allows for the highest possible flexibility and appears as an attractive direction for future research to optimize not only the cost per transmitted bit but also security and power consumption aspects.

Among the different solutions to increase the available bandwidth, using bands beyond the traditional C band seems like the most mature option [2]. Furthermore, low-cost pluggable transponders operating in bands beyond the C band, enable cost-sensitive hybrid-domain applications, i.e. with optical fibers carrying traffic which may be simultaneously access/metro and core. In this context, monitoring and the construction of the network digital twin becomes important in the optimization of the optical network. Additionally, the exploitation of multicarrier modulation, such as orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM), enhances network flexibility by considering sub- and super- wavelength granularity [3].

In this paper, we focus on the wide-band monitoring of chromatic dispersion (CD) by means of multi band (MB) optical OFDM bandwidth/bit rate variable transceivers (BVTs) adapted to access/metro networks, i.e. over C+L+S bands. We consider the experimental testbed of [4].

Methodology

The linear OFDM channel has a transfer function given analytically as [5]:

$$H_{\text{eq}} = \cos\left(\frac{\pi \cdot (f \cdot \lambda)^2 \cdot D(\lambda) \cdot L}{c}\right) \quad (1)$$

where f is the frequency, λ the channel central wavelength, $D(\lambda)$ is the dispersion parameter

and L is the length of the lightpath. Eq. (1) corresponds to a sinusoidal variation and notches (zeros) are a function of accumulated dispersion $D(\lambda) \cdot L$

$$\frac{(f \cdot \lambda)^2 \cdot D(\lambda) \cdot L}{c} = \kappa + 1/2 \quad (2)$$

with κ an integer. In our OFDM system, we monitor power spectrum density (PSD) of received signal in the positive frequency part of the received samples which is expected to fit with the square of the transfer function of Eq. (1). Estimating CD properties of a fiber link can be therefore performed in the following: a) for each lightpath with central wavelength λ_j we record a 2048-point power spectral density (PSD) vs. frequency b) we use a moving average filter with block size of 15 to smooth the monitored PSD c) we calculate the notches (the zeros in the PSD vs. frequency) in a least mean square fashion by setting as a starting point the accumulated CD given the datasheet fiber type and the measured fiber length, d) we compute through Eq. (1) the accumulated CD_j corresponding to the wavelength λ_j . e) Each link dispersion can be estimated by using correlation between lightpath accumulated dispersions [6]. f) from the measured curve of accumulated link CD vs. frequency we compute the dispersion parameter D vs. frequency curve, assuming a perfect knowledge of the fiber length L , and finally g) we fit the curve D vs. λ with a derived three-term Sellmeier formula of the relative group delay [7]:

$$D(\lambda) = \frac{S_0}{4} \left(\lambda - \frac{\lambda_0^4}{\lambda^3} \right) \quad (3)$$

where λ_0 is the zero-dispersion wavelength and S_0 is the dispersion slope at λ_0 .

Measurement accuracy

To establish the validity of the method, we first study the accuracy of the method on different fiber types, i.e. standard single mode fiber (SSMF) and Teralight (TL) with different fiber lengths (50 and 75 km) and in three optical bands S, C and L. The transceiver is an OFDM-based MB BVT,

Fig. 2: Power spectral density of detected signal after 75 km of propagation in standard single mode fiber. Crosses are experimental points; dashed line is the fit based on Eq. 4.

as depicted in Fig. 5 [3]. The DSP block, at the transmitter, includes data parallelization and mapping (i.e. 4 QAM modulation format for each subcarrier), insertion of training symbols (TS), implementation of a 512-point inverse fast Fourier transform, insertion of cyclic prefix (CP), serialization, and radio frequency (RF) up-conversion. The transmitted signals have a 20 GHz- bandwidth, and works at different spectral bands. A high-speed DAC working at 64 GSa/s is considered to create double side band (DSB) OFDM signals. External modulation is implemented by means of a Mach Zehnder modulator (MZM) and a tuneable laser source (TLS). After propagation in optical fiber, the signal is amplified with a doped fiber amplifier (x DFA), filtered, and sampled by direct detection on 50 GSa/s digital oscilloscope with 20 GHz bandwidth (see Fig. 5). Erbium DFAs (EDFAs) are used for the L band and C band, whereas thulium DFA (TDFA) is considered for the S-band. The receiver OFDM-based DSP for performance evaluation is detailed in [3]. However, here we focus on the CD evaluation by including at the bandwidth/bit rate variable receiver (BVRx) monitoring capabilities without

Fig. 3: Dispersion parameter D as a function of the wavelength obtained from the fitting with Eq. (4) for different fiber types and fiber lengths. Red dashed lines are the results of the fit with Eq. (3) for each fiber type. Inset: histogram of the estimation error.

Tab. 1: Tested fiber type, length and fitted parameters.

Fiber	Length [km]	λ_0 [nm]	S_0 [ps/(km.nm ²)]
SSMF	50	1335	0.0968
	75	1337	0.0966
TL	50	1416	0.0703

necessarily activating the receiver OFDM-based DSP. In particular, to evaluate the CD for the different bands, we vary the central wavelength of TLS within each band before capturing data for different fiber types and fiber lengths. For each acquisition, at the receiver DSP block of Fig. 5, we perform a 2048-point PSD and adjust by fitting with a function accounting the linear OFDM channel of Eq. (1) and the scope bandwidth:

$$PSD(f) = P_0 \left| \cos \left((f\lambda)^2 \frac{D_\lambda * L}{c} \right) \right|^2 10^{\alpha * f} + N_0, \quad (4)$$

where α is an attenuation coefficient related to the scope bandwidth, N_0 is accounting for multiple electrical and optical noise and is a background level, D_λ is the dispersion coefficient at the wavelength λ , L the fiber length. α is fixed for all the experiment 0.2 dB.GHz^{-1} . Fig. 2 shows a typical PSD (cross markers) with fitted curve from Eq. (4) in dashed line.

The results of this fit for all the fiber types, lengths, and channel wavelengths are plotted in Fig. 3. For each fiber type, we perform a fit with the Eq. (3) by minimizing the root mean square error with the data to determine the fiber parameters λ_0 and S_0 . The resulted fit is plotted with dashed red line in Fig. 3. The obtained parameters for each fiber type and length are displayed in Tab. 1. The curve well fits the data for SSMF but seems to deviate at low wavelengths for TL. This is due to the limited accuracy in the low accumulated dispersion area where the notch frequency approaches the signal bandwidth. Finally, the inset of Fig. 3 shows the histogram of the errors illustrating an overall good performance of the methods with a standard deviation of $0.19 \text{ ps}/(\text{km.nm})$ and a mean value of $-0.03 \text{ ps}/(\text{km.nm})$.

Experimental Testbed Integration

Within the ADRENALINE testbed of [4], detailed on Fig. 5b), we integrate our monitoring solution to a software-defined networking (SDN) controller. The testbed is composed of four Nodes operating in the C-band connected via heterogeneous fiber. The 35 km links are SMF, the 50 km link is TL and 150 km is LEAF. We ask the controller to establish a new service between distinct node (dashed green line on the topology on Fig. 5a). After performing the adequate devices configuration and establishing the connectivity, the SDN

Fig. 5: Experimental setup for CD monitoring. (a) GUI of the SDN controller to establish the optical path. (b) Setup used to perform the experiment with the MB-SBVT: The OFDM data are generated, sent through the optical testbed or Fiber spool, amplified, filtered, and then sampled by an oscilloscope. The monitored data are sent to the controller via the SDN agent.

agent of the MB BVRx reports the PSD of the detected signal to the SDN controller. The controller stores each measurement with additional route information (used link, wavelength). For each measurement, the fit with Eq. (4) is performed and lead to the accumulated dispersion $D \cdot L$ of the route at the given channel wavelength. When enough lightpaths have been established, the application solves the CD per link at each wavelength using a correlation algorithm as in [6]. An example of stored values is shown in Fig. 6b highlighted in with the dispersion parameter at a frequency of 193.1 THz. Finally, fiber link wavelength dependent parameters are extracted as shown earlier.

We established 29 new services, all starting from Node 3 and egressing at Node 1, Node 2, Node 4 (via Node 1 or 2). The routes N3-N1 and N3-N2 corresponds to a link, therefore determining their properties does not require the correlation algorithm. However, determining the ones of links N1-N4 and N2-N4 require the correlation algorithm. Fig. 6a shows the obtained dispersion parameter for each link (see measurement markers). The red dashed lines are the ones from

a)

Fig. 3. Note that the link N2-N4 is the TL fiber spool characterized in the previous section. For TL fiber (red stars), we estimate the properties via the correlation algorithm, and we see it overlaps very well (standard deviation of 0.18 ps/(nm.km)) with previous characterization. Another interest of such monitoring is the observation of a deviation to the average fiber parameters in the link N3-N2.

The last step consists in using the updated and accurate chromatic dispersion in the path computation function of the SDN controller, as the traffic engineering metric, in order to weight the path in favour of a low accumulated dispersion for such double side band transmitter.

Conclusions

We develop a technique to monitor the chromatic dispersion characteristics of fiber with an OFDM MB BVT. We demonstrate its accuracy and a small standard deviation of 0.19 ps/(km.nm). We integrate our monitoring solution in an optical networking testbed with a complete workflow.

b)

Fig. 6: (a) Dispersion parameter D as a function of the wavelength obtained from the fitting with Eq. (4) for different fiber types and fiber lengths. Red dashed line is the results of Fig. 3. (b) Updated link properties in the controller graphical interface.

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